

Digital Payment System in India: Development and Future Consideration

Dr. Satish Manikarao Dhoke

Assistant Professor,

Department of Commerce,

Moreshwar Arts, Science & Commerce College Bhokardan Dist; Jalana.

satishdhokecommerce@gmail.com

Abstract:

This research paper aims to explore in India a digital payment system, and thus identify development and future consideration. The paper discusses conceptual framework, digital payment platforms, instruments and services available in the economy and their robustness. The also defines strategies to overcome the challenges faced by the economy in digitizing the financial system. The present research paper is focusing on the impact of these new digital payments systems on customers and problems encountered if any.

Keyword:-Digital payment, Cashless system, Online payment, Payment Systems, Mobile Payments

Introduction:

Digital payment is a way of payment which is made through digital modes. In digital payments, payer and payee both use digital modes to send and receive money. It is also called electronic payment. No hard cash is involved in the digital payments. All the transactions in digital payments are completed online. It is an instant and convenient way to make payments.

If we talk about cash payments, you have to first withdraw cash from your account. Then you use this cash to pay at shops. Shopkeeper goes to the bank to deposit the cash which he got from you. This process is time-consuming for you and also for the shopkeeper. But in digital payments, the money transfers from your account to the shopkeeper's account immediately. This process is automatic and neither you nor the shopkeeper is required to visit the bank.

Digital payments save you from long queues of ATMs and banks. Because, if you pay digitally, you won't need to withdraw cash from your account. It also lots of time and a little bit money as well. In order to address all these, payment systems have evolved from barter to currency, to digital systems. We are witnessing enormous change in the payment systems, disrupting the monopoly of physical/paper-based system by electronic ones. Digital payment is a way of payment which is made through digital modes. In digital payments, payer and payee both use digital modes to send and receive money. It is also called electronic payment. No hard cash is involved in the digital payments. The payment system in any country needs to pass the litmus test of safety, security, soundness, efficiency, and accessibility. All the transactions in digital payments are completed online. It is an instant and convenient way to make payments. Digital payments save you from long queues of ATMs and banks.

Objectives

- To know the different modes of e -payment.
- To know the development and future consideration of e- payment system in India.
- To identify the future of digital payment.
- To know whether the people are aware of Digital payment system.
- To understand the security system.

Advantages of Digital Payments

1. Easy and convenient: Digital payments are easy and convenient. You do not need to take loads of cash with you. All you need is your mobile phone or Aadhaar number or a card to pay. UPI apps and E-Wallets made digital payments easier.

2. Pay or send money from anywhere: With digital payment modes, you can pay from anywhere anytime. Suppose your close friend's mother fell ill at night. He called you at midnight and asked some money. Don't worry, you can send money to your friend using digital payment modes such as UPI apps, USSD or E-Wallets.

3. Discounts from taxes: Government has announced many discounts to encourage digital payments. If you use digital modes to make a payment up to Rs. 2000, you get full exemption from service tax. You also get 0.75% discounts on fuels and 10% discount on insurance premiums of government insurers.

4. Written record: You often forget to note down your cash spending. Or even if you note, it takes a lot of time. But you do not need to note your spending every time with digital payments. These are automatically recorded in your passbook or inside your E-Wallet app. This helps to maintain your record, track your spending and budget planning.

5. Less Risk: Digital payments have less risk if you use them wisely. If you lose your mobile phone or debit/credit card or Andhra card you don't have to worry a lot. No one can use your money without MPIN, PIN or your fingerprint in the case of Andhra. But it is advised that you should get your card blocked if you lost it. Also call the helpline of your E-wallet to suspend the wallet account to prevent anyone from using your wallet money.

Development of digital payment system in India

In the reform of prime minister narendramodi has pushed India's to adopt cashless transaction given the digital payment sector a significant boost. Government has announced many discounts to encourage digital payments. If you use digital modes to make a payment up to Rs. 2000, you get full exemption from service tax. You also get 0.75% discounts on fuels and 10% discount on insurance premiums of government.

Modes of Digital Payments:

- **E Wallets**

Mobile wallets are digital instruments where you can store money for instant payments. You load money from your bank account via credit/debit cards or net banking. Most wallets are semi closed wallets ,Paytm, Freechargeetc

- **UPI**

Unified payments Interface AppsUnified Payments Interface (UPI) is a paymentsystem launched by National PaymentsCorporation of India and regulated by Reserve

Unified Payment Interface is an electronic funds transfer instrument that enables all bank account holders to send and receive money from their smartphones without the need to enter bank account information or net banking user id/password. This requires only the recipient's mobile number or Virtual Payment Address (VPA). UPI is an advanced version of Immediate Payment Service(IMPS) platform designed for transferring funds using: Transfer through Virtual Payment Address (Unique ID provided by bank) or Account Number + IFSC or

Mobile Number +MMID(Mobile Money Identifier) or Aadhaar Number or Collect / Pull money basis Virtual ID. A MPIN (Mobile banking Personal Identification number) is given to the banking customer once they register for UPI which is required to be entered while confirming a money transfer. Banks supporting UPI payment have started to upload their own UPI enabled Apps on Google Play store as well as on Apple App Store also.[National Payments Corporation of India has launched a Payment app BHIM and NUUP service for performing transaction using Aadhaar number over UPI

• **Plastic Money**

Plastic money means **debit cards and credit cards** that are used at ATM's for cash withdrawal and POS machines while shopping. Having a debit or credit card makes you burden free from carrying cash. Also risk of theft goes down to zero as it needs a PIN to carry out transactions. You don't need to carry huge amount of cash with you. Just swipe and go. Debit card payments are made through bank account. Bank account gets debited while paying using debit card. But in case of a credit card, it is a monthly postpaid bill payment system that takes place. Debit/Credit Cards etc.

• **Net Banking**

Net banking is another way for making transactions electronically. All you need is a bank account with e banking facility enabled on it. You can transfer funds to others account from the comfort of your home. There is no need of going to your bank to get transfers done. You can make all payments and transfers yourself. This is a very convenient way to go cashless in India as well, eg. Online Fund Transfer.

• **Aadhaar Card**

Aadhaar Enabled Payment System is a way to get money from the bank account. This system of getting money neither requires your signature nor Debit card. You don't even need to visit a bank branch for getting money through the Aadhaar Enabled Payment System. Rather, it uses Aadhaar data for the authentication. Like UPI and USSD, this is another initiative by the NPCI.

Research Methodology

The research methodology used is explorative study which includes and secondary data, the study based on secondary information/data. Different journals, newspapers, books and relevant websites have been consulted in order to make the study an effective one. The present study is an attempt to examine the E- payment system in India.

Findings

- People are more aware about the online payments through mobile applications and there is a wider increase in growth rate.
- Due to advanced feature in pay tm and pay u money net banking has been directly replaced.
- Pay tm and Pay u Money is giving 2 level security authentication to safeguard our payment details.
- Pay Tm Company has come across the customer problems immediately while making payments.
- Pay tm and Pay u money is providing easy payment structures compared to Digital payment system.

Suggestions

- People should be more accurate about refunding their amount directly to their wallet if any delay in payment.
- People should update their pay tm or pay u money applications from time to time in order to safeguard.
- Users should be more careful about the offers, cash backs provided by pay tm or pay u money.
- The digital payment system has to take necessary steps to overcome delay in processing of payments.

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